

PARTICIPATORY MAPPING IN MONCHIQUE

OBJECTIVE

Identify, locate and interpret the local risk and vulnerability areas, beginning a reflection about critical issues related to the **rural fire risk prevention**.

METHOD

Figure 1 | Five steps of the participatory mapping process applied by the BRIDGE project in Monchique.

WORKSHOPS

- ◆ **Students** from the **8th grade** from **Escola Manuel Nascimento** (21.03.2022)
- ◆ **Rural landowners** that are members of **Monchique Alerta** (21.03.2022)
- ◆ **Rural landowners** that are members of **Aspaflobal** and of **Coopachique** (26.04.2022)
- ◆ **Rural landowners** that are members of **A Nossa Terra** (27.04.2022)

RESULTS

1. Fire risk and local vulnerabilities factors that were discussed in the workshops:

Figure 2 | First result from the participatory mapping workshops in Monchique.

2. Final map reflecting the data, collected in the workshops, able to be spatialized.

Figure 3 | Second result from the participatory mapping workshops in Monchique.

3. Reflection on possible measures to be implemented in Monchique:

- ◆ Carry out an in-depth study on the rural lands with forest production in Monchique.
- ◆ Assess the current access conditions of landowners to water points and reservoirs and improve access logistic to the nearby housing.
- ◆ Promote population awareness projects (land clearing, plantation, etc.).
- ◆ Re-evaluate and revise the Policies, Plans and Programs that regulate the forest territories use, occupation and management.
- ◆ Promote new patterns of use and occupation of the territory that are more centred around biodiversity and family agriculture.
- ◆ Require companies that rent private land for forest production to present, before license granting, a post-production recovery plan.
- ◆ Build a biomass plant in Monchique.
- ◆ Create a Firefighting Certificate for the rural landowners.

